

1 A comprehensive item bank of internal validity issues of relevance to *in vitro* toxicology
2 studies

3 Gunn E. Vist^{1,2†}, Heather M.R. Ames^{1,2}, Gro H. Mathisen¹, Trine Husøy^{1,3}, Camilla
4 Svendsen^{1,4}, Anna Beronius⁵, Emma Di Consiglio⁶, Ingrid L. Druwe⁷, Thomas Hartung^{8,9},
5 Sebastian Hoffmann^{10,11}, Carlijn R. Hooijmans¹², Kyriaki Machera¹³, Pilar Prieto¹⁴, Joshua F.
6 Robinson¹⁵, Erwin Roggen¹⁶, Andrew A. Rooney¹⁷, Nicolas Roth^{18,19}, Eliana Spilioti¹³,
7 Anastasia Spyropoulou¹³, Olga Tcheremenskaia⁶, Emanuela Testai⁶, Mathieu Vinken²⁰, Paul
8 Whaley^{1,21†}

9
10 ¹Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment, Norwegian Institute of Public
11 Health, Oslo, Norway.

12 ²Division for Health Services, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway.

13 ³Department of Food Safety, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway.

14 ⁴Department of Chemical Toxicology, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway.

15 ⁵Institute of Environmental Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden.

16 ⁶Environment & Health Department, Italian National Institute of Health (ISS), Rome, Italy.

17 ⁷United States Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Research and Development,
18 Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessments, Research Triangle Park, NC,
19 USA.

20 ⁸Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing, Johns Hopkins University, Bloomberg School of
21 Public Health, Baltimore, MD, USA.

22 ⁹CAAT Europe, University of Konstanz, Konstanz, Germany.

23 ¹⁰Evidence-based toxicology collaboration, Johns Hopkins University, Bloomberg School of
24 Public Health, Baltimore, MD, USA.

25 ¹¹seh consulting + services, Paderborn, Germany.

26 ¹²Department of Anesthesiology, Pain and Palliative Care, Radboud University Medical
27 Centre, Nijmegen, Netherlands.

28 ¹³Laboratory of Toxicological Control of Pesticides, Scientific Directorate of Pesticides'
29 Control and Phytopharmacy, Benaki Phytopathological Institute, Kifissia, Greece.

30 ¹⁴European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Ispra, Italy.

31 ¹⁵Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology & Reproductive Sciences, University of California,
32 San Francisco (UCSF), USA.

33 ¹⁶3Rs Management and Consulting ApS, Lyngby, Denmark.

34 ¹⁷Division of Translational Toxicology, National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences,
35 Research Triangle Park, NC, USA.

36 ¹⁸Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland.

37 ¹⁹Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology.

38 ²⁰Department of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Vrije Universiteit Brussel;
39 Belgium.

40 ²¹Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK.

41 †Correspondence should be addressed to Gunn E. Vist; E-mail: gunn.vist@fhi.no.

42 †Correspondence should be addressed to Paul Whaley; E-mail: paul@whaleyresearch.uk.

43 Disclaimers

44 The author Ingrid L. Druwe is employed at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. The
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51 Abstract

52 **Context:** *In vitro* toxicology studies are increasingly being included as evidence in
53 systematic reviews and chemical risk assessments. INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the
54 internal validity of *in vitro* studies, is currently under development. The first step in
55 developing INVITES-IN involves the creation of an “item bank”, ~~an overview database~~ of
56 study assessment concepts that may be relevant to evaluating the internal validity of *in vitro*
57 toxicology studies. The item bank and ~~its development~~ methodology [for its creation](#)
58 presented in this manuscript are intended to be a general resource for supporting [the](#)

59 ~~development of appraisal tools for the design and conduct of~~ *in vitro* toxicology studies and
60 potentially other ~~related~~ study designs.

61 **Methods:** We derived the item bank from seven literature sources (one existing item bank
62 created from a systematic review of assessment criteria for *in vitro* studies, and six
63 purposively sampled study appraisal tools) and the transcribed ~~discussions~~ ~~pts~~ of three focus
64 groups. Assessment criteria plausibly relating to internal validity were abstracted from the
65 literature sources and focus group transcripts, disaggregated into individual criteria, then
66 normalised to express in the simplest achievable language the core issue in each criterion –
67 an “item bank” of assessment concepts. The items were then mapped onto a set of bias
68 domains. We conducted simple descriptive statistical analyses and visualisations to describe
69 patterns in the ~~data~~ ~~set~~ ~~base~~ and developed ~~ed~~ recommendations for the use and development of
70 the item bank.

71 **Results:** The item bank contains 405 items ~~that may be important for of potential relevance to~~
72 evaluating the internal validity of *in vitro* toxicology studies. ~~The inclusion of focus group~~
73 ~~discussions with in vitro experts was of significant value in our method, adding more than a~~
74 ~~hundred additional bias items~~ ~~The original systematic review contributed 96 items to the item~~
75 ~~bank before removing duplicates between the systematic review and the six tools and the~~
76 ~~focus groups. The tools specifically designed for assessing the internal validity of studies~~
77 ~~added 215 items. The focus groups added an additional 114 items.~~

78 **Discussion:** To our knowledge, this is the second item bank of any kind to have been
79 created for toxicology studies, and the first to use focus groups as a data source alongside
80 literature analysis. ~~This two-prong approach is to comprehensively identify issues that relate~~
81 ~~to the internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies.~~ The large number of items contributed by
82 focus group discussions suggests this is an efficient method for capturing internal validity
83 issues that are not easily identifiable in the literature, ~~if present at all~~. We believe our item
84 bank and methodology for its creation will be a useful resource for supporting the informing
85 the development of appraisal tools of future tools, or updating of existing tools, that target the
86 internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies. Due to the broad applicability of many items in
87 the item bank, it may be informative for study designs beyond the *in vitro* domain.

88 1.4 Introduction

89 Systematic reviews are increasingly being conducted in toxicology, environmental
90 health, and chemical risk assessment (Menon et al., 2022). An important part of the
91 review methodology is the evaluation of internal validity, i.e. the extent to which the

92 design, conduct, and reporting of a study are likely to have prevented bias. While many tools
93 have been created for assessing validity of in vitro studies, to date there is no consensus as
94 to which, if any, of these tools ought to be used for the assessment of internal validity of in
95 vitro studies (Tran et al., 2021). To address this issue, we are conducting the INVITES-IN
96 (IN VITro Experimental Studies Internal validity) project. The objective of INVITES-IN is to
97 select, modify, or develop an appraisal tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro
98 studies, with an initial focus on eukaryotic cell culture studies.

99 As internal validity cannot be directly measured, INVITES-IN is being designed to address
100 risk for introduction of different types of bias to in vitro studies. Bias is a systematic error, or
101 deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual studies or across studies, and
102 may be introduced through limitations in the design, conduct, or reporting of a study. Bias
103 items are study properties/concepts that may be relevant for introduction of bias. We will
104 follow the framework of general principles for developing quality assessment tools as
105 suggested by Whiting et al. (2017), recommending an "item generation" step be part of tool
106 development methodology. A comprehensive overview of study characteristics identified as
107 having the potential to introduce bias to in vitro studies, called an "item bank", will therefore
108 be prepared and used as the starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN. The item bank is
109 intended to be functioning as an extendable dataset created using a reproducible method
110 and provide a common resource from which specific tools can be derived. An item bank was
111 part of the method for updating of the PRISMA reporting checklist for systematic reviews in
112 2020 by Page et al. (2020), and the methodology is further developed by Whaley et al.

Commented [GHM1]: Paul - can you insert the link to the reference?

113 The creation of INVITES-IN consists of four methodological stages, that we refer to as
114 "studies":

- 115 • Study 1. Creating a comprehensive database of issues that may affect the internal
116 validity of in vitro studies of any design.
- 117 • Study 2. Prioritising issues from the database according to their relevance to the
118 assessment of internal validity of eukaryotic cell culture systems.
- 119 • Study 3. Creating a beta version of an appraisal tool based on analysis of the prioritised
120 issues identified in stage 2.

- 121 • [Study 4. Creating a final release version of the tool, based on user-testing of the beta](#)
122 [version.](#)

123 [Due to the complexity of the INVITES-IN project, we are publishing our methods and results](#)
124 [in three manuscripts. The present manuscript describes the methods and results for Study 1.](#)
125 [A second manuscript will describe Study 2. The third manuscript will describe Studies 3 and](#)
126 [4. The planned methods for all four INVITES-IN studies, the creation and user testing of](#)
127 [INVITES-IN are described in two protocols \(Mathisen et al., 2023; Svendsen et al., 2023\).](#)

128 [1.1 ~~2~~-Objectives](#)

129 [The objective of this study is to create a comprehensive database of issues relating to the](#)
130 [design, conduct, or reporting of *in vitro* studies that may introduce bias into their results or](#)
131 [findings. Following Page et al. \(2020\) and Whiting et al. \(2017\), we call such a database an](#)
132 ["item bank".](#) ~~[To provide an organisational structure of the item bank, bias domains were](#)
133 [used as a conceptual framework. Bias domains are themes such as e.g. study performance,](#)
134 [analysis, and reporting, under which bias items can be organised.](#)~~

135
136 ~~[This publication is a methods and dataset manuscript. It is intended to be of interest to other](#)
137 [tool developers who may wish to apply our method in other contexts, use our item bank for](#)
138 [developing their own tools, or extend or update our item bank.](#)~~

139
140 [It should be noted that while INVITES-IN is ultimately aimed at creating a tool for assessing](#)
141 [risk of bias in studies of eukaryotic cell culture systems, the item bank includes issues for *in*](#)
142 [vitro studies of any design.](#)

143 ~~[The following studies and related activities are being conducted to develop INVITES-IN:](#)~~

144 ~~[the generation of a comprehensive list of issues relating to the internal validity of *in vitro*](#)
145 [toxicology studies \(the present item bank study\)](#)~~

146 ~~[the prioritisation of the relative importance of the issues in relation to their potential impact](#)
147 [on bias in the results and findings of *in vitro* studies \(a modified Delphi study, currently](#)
148 [ongoing\)](#)~~

149 ~~[the creation of a beta version of INVITES-IN](#)~~

150 ~~[the user testing and creation of the release version of INVITES-IN.](#)~~

151 ~~Two protocols, one describing the design of INVITES-IN and one describing the~~
152 ~~performance evaluation of INVITES-IN, have been published (Mathisen et al., 2023a;~~
153 ~~Svensden et al., 2023)-~~

154 ~~The objective of the present study is to create a database of issues that researchers~~
155 ~~have identified as having the potential to introduce bias into the results or findings of an *in*~~
156 ~~*vitro* study, hereafter referred to as an “item bank”. An item bank was part of the method for~~
157 ~~updating of the PRISMA reporting checklist for systematic reviews in 2020 by Page et al.~~
158 ~~(2020)-~~

159 ~~The creation of the internal validity item bank is part of the project “Next Generation Risk~~
160 ~~Assessment in Practice” (VKM, 2023). The project is part of the European Partnership for~~
161 ~~the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) (PARC, 2023). A project group (PG) has~~
162 ~~been established with the responsibility to create the tool for assessing internal validity. A~~
163 ~~scientific advisory group (SAG) consisting of experts in methods for tool development,~~
164 ~~systematic review (SR) methods, chemical risk assessment, toxicology, and/or *in vitro*~~
165 ~~models has been established to provide the PG with strategic guidance and support.~~

166 2. ~~32~~ Methods

167 ~~In their proposed framework for developing quality assessment tools, Whiting and~~
168 ~~colleagues recommend an “item generation” step be part of tool development methodology~~
169 ~~(Whiting et al., 2017). However, what constitutes best practice in item generation is not, as~~
170 ~~far as we are aware, a settled matter. Our item bank development methodology follows ~~e~~~~
171 ~~(Whaley et al., 2024) ~~Whaley et al. 2024~~ Whaley et al. (2024) and consists of the ~~three~~ two~~
172 ~~main stages, summarised ~~described~~ below then described more fully in the subsequent~~
173 ~~sections of this manuscript. The full details of the methodology are in our preregistered~~
174 ~~study protocol (Svensden et al., 2023).~~

175 Stage 1. Issue ~~D~~discovery

176 ~~What: The objective of this stage is to ~~identification of a~~ comprehensive set of ~~study~~~~
177 ~~~~characteristics relating to~~ issues relating to the design, conduct, or reporting of *in vitro* studies~~
178 ~~that may introduce bias into their results or findings.~~

179 ~~How: Our method for this stage is to abstract from (a) ~~a~~ Using both a purposive literature~~
180 ~~purposive sample of tools designed for assessing the internal validity of scientific studies and~~
181 ~~(b) focus group transcripts ~~to generate a comprehensive list of appraisal criteria~~ issues that~~
182 ~~researchers believe ~~is~~ used by tools for evaluating the internal validity of research and focus~~

Commented [PW2]: Whaley P, Blain RB, Draper D, Rooney AA, Walker VR, Wattam S, Wright R, Hooijmans CR. 2024 Jul 4. Identifying assessment criteria for *in vitro* studies: a method and item bank. Toxicol Sci. doi:10.1093/toxsci/kfae083. http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfae083.

183 ~~groups to identify additional study characteristics that may introduce bias to *in vitro*~~
184 ~~studies impact the internal validity of *in vitro* studies.~~

185 Why:

186 ~~Since~~We chose this approach because three separate reviews have indicated that ~~none of~~
187 ~~the existing quality assessment tools for *in vitro* studies individually cover all critical aspects~~
188 ~~for assessing the internal validity~~~~systematic review of *in vitro* studies~~ (Paiva Barbosa et al.,
189 2023; Tran et al., 2021; Whaley et al., 2024). ~~we decided to build the item bank on both~~
190 ~~existing validity assessment tools to capture bias items already incorporated in existing tools,~~
191 ~~and on the~~ ~~and~~ ~~we believed~~ ~~experiences of~~ ~~that~~ ~~focus groups with *in vitro* experts would~~ ~~to~~
192 ~~capture important bias items issues that may have not yet have been incorporated into~~
193 ~~validity assessment tools.~~

194 **Stage 2. Issue Analysis**

195 ~~What: Deriving~~The objective of this stage is to derive ~~linguistically minimalist expressions of~~
196 ~~the study assessment concepts identified in the discovery phase~~stage 1 (i.e. create the
197 ~~database of "items"), and organising these according to bias themes~~~~thematically.~~

198 ~~How:~~We chose this approach because the way that bias issues are presented in appraisal
199 ~~tools and focus group discussions is heterogeneous and complex. This can make it~~
200 ~~challenging to discern precisely what issue is being addressed by a criterion in a tool or a~~
201 ~~point of expert discussion, and to compare tool criteria or discussion points to determine if~~
202 ~~they are in fact about the same issue.~~

203 ~~We therefore~~ ~~Disaggregation~~~~disaggregated~~ ~~of complex appraisal criteria into their~~
204 ~~component issues and sought to eliminate~~ ~~ion of irrelevant linguistic differences in how~~
205 ~~appraisal criteria are expressed in different tools and contexts (a process we refer to as~~
206 ~~"normalisation")~~ ~~appraisal tools;~~ ~~and~~ ~~We also~~ ~~thematic organisation~~ ~~organised~~ ~~of items into~~
207 ~~bias domains~~ to help structure the database and make it easier to use in later stages of the
208 ~~INVITES-IN project.~~

209 The process for issue analysis is illustrated in Figure 1.

210 ~~Why: Avoid including a long list of complex items that are difficult to analyse in the item bank~~
211 ~~and supporting later analysis and use.~~

212 **Stage 3. Reporting**

213 ~~What: Presentation of the item bank and giving recommendations for use~~
214 ~~Why: Increase the usability of the item bank for this project and for other researchers~~
215 ~~This is illustrated in Figure 1 and described in more detail in Sections 2.1 and 2.2. The full~~
216 ~~details of the methodology are in the preregistered study protocol (Svendson et al., 2023).~~

217 2.1 Discovery

218 We used two sources for creation of the item bank: first, literature (six appraisal tools and
219 one systematic review, see section 2.1.1 for more details); and second, experts with
220 extensive experience with *in vitro* studies (called “domain experts”) participating in focus
221 group discussions (see section 2.1.2). We conducted the literature analysis first, then
222 supplemented the literature with the additional items discovered through the focus group
223 discussions. ~~This is an extension of the item bank development methodology developed by~~
224 ~~Whaley and Hooijmans (2023).~~

225 2.1.1 Literature review sources

226 Items were abstracted from the literature sources as listed in the protocol (Svendson et al.,
227 2023) with one additional tool (ROBINS-E). The literature sources included a selection of
228 published and widely used validity assessment tools, and an existing item bank covering
229 study appraisal concepts included in 67 *in vitro* appraisal tools (Whaley et al., 2023).

230 The literature sources included tools for assessment of *in vitro* studies, human studies, and
231 animal experimental studies. We included assessment tools for non *in vitro* studies based on
232 our experience that assessment concepts are quite generalizable for different types of study,
233 and therefore that newer risk of bias tools even for epidemiological research may include
234 concepts that could be applicable to *in vitro* studies. This way we aimed to capture emerging
235 developments in risk of bias assessment methods and criteria that ~~could potentially be~~
236 ~~applicable to *in vitro* study designs but~~ may not yet have been incorporated into tools within
237 the *in vitro* toxicology literature. ~~One source that was listed in the protocol (Tran et al., 2021)~~
238 ~~was removed (see changes from protocol section).~~ The ~~tools~~ literature sources are listed in
239 Table 1.

240 ~~Study assessment criteria judged as potentially relating to internal validity were~~
241 ~~independently abstracted by two investigators (CEV and PW). Differences in abstraction~~
242 ~~decisions were resolved through discussion between the two investigators, a process~~
243 ~~referred to as “reconciliation”.~~

244 **Table 1. The literature sources for item bank.**

Source study ID	Source Tool Name or Title	Source Type of tool	Source Citation
EPA (2022) IRIS	IRIS: ORD Staff Handbook for Developing IRIS Assessments	Bias assessment tool Guidance on study appraisal for IRIS assessments	EPA (2022)
NTP OHAT (2015) OHAT	OHAT: Protocol to evaluate the evidence for an association between perfluorooctanic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) exposure and immunotoxicity	Bias assessment tool	(NTP OHAT, 2015) NTP OHAT (2015)
Sterne et al. (2019) ROB2	ROB 2: A revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials	Bias assessment tool	Sterne et al. (2019)
ROBINS-E Development Group et al. (2023) ROBINS-E	ROBINS-E: Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Exposure	Bias assessment tool	Higgins et al. (2024)
Roth et al. (2021) SciRAP	SciRAP: Development of the SciRAP Approach for Evaluating the Reliability and Relevance of <i>in vitro</i> Toxicity Data	Bias assessment tool Study appraisal tool for supporting risk assessment	Roth et al. (2021)
Cooper et al. (2016) Cooper	Study sensitivity: Evaluating the ability to detect effects in systematic reviews of chemical exposures	Guidance on assessing study Ssensitivity assessment tool -	Cooper et al. (2016)
Whaley et al. (2023) Whaley	Literature-based discovery of assessment criteria for <i>in vitro</i> studies: a method and item bank	PRIVAT-i item bank	Whaley et al. (2023)

Commented [GEV3]: Referanser. Tusen takk

245 [2.1.2 Focus groups](#)

246 [2.12.2.1 Recruitment of focus group ~~discussion~~ participants](#)

247 Eligible focus group discussion participants were scientists with or without ~~SR-systematic~~
248 ~~review~~ experience that are active in the field of *in vitro* studies in academia, governmental
249 institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes) or private research
250 institutes, at postdoctoral level or higher, and level B1 English speakers. By “active in the
251 field of *in vitro* studies” we mean having practical experience in conducting *in vitro* studies,
252 and/or experience in analysing or evaluating data from such studies.

253 The focus group discussion participants were nominated by members in the project group
254 and the scientific advisory group (see “project governance”).

255 Potential participants were invited to participate with the aim of ~~creating three groups~~
256 ~~with achieving~~ (1) an equal gender distribution, (2) a reasonable demographic and regional
257 distribution, and (3) ~~enough participants to have three groups of a group size of~~ six to eight
258 ~~participants/people~~. Potential participants were contacted via email and ~~received-sent~~
259 information about the project, the purpose of the focus group discussions and the method,
260 that the results would be anonymised, the withdrawal procedure, the financial source, and
261 the approximate time for the focus group discussions (Supplemental Material 1). Thirty
262 ~~potentially eligible invitations participants~~ were ~~sent~~ invited in the period of 16 May to 12 June
263 2023. All participants who accepted the invitation actively confirmed their consent to
264 participate in the research.

265 ~~A total of twenty participants were recruited and participated in the focus group discussions:~~
266 ~~six in group 1, eight in group 2, and six in group 3. Twenty participants were recruited and~~
267 ~~participated in the focus group discussions: six in group 1, eight in group 2, and six in group~~
268 ~~3~~. An overview of the characteristics of the participants is given in Supplemental Material 2.
269 The participants were mostly from Europe and North America, and worked in various sectors
270 (~~e.g.i.e.~~ government ~~agencies~~, academia). Most had extensive expertise with *in vitro* studies
271 and chemical risk assessment. While we sought to have an equal distribution of gender, the
272 individuals who had the expertise along with availability to participate were overwhelmingly
273 female (15 female to 5 males).

274 [2.12.2.2 Focus group discussion sessions](#)

275 Focus group participants were engaged in open-ended ~~on-line discussions converstation~~
276 ~~of about~~ how, in their opinion, bias can be introduced into *in vitro* studies. Each focus group
277 met twice ~~virtually~~, for 90 minutes in each meeting, ~~using Microsoft Teams~~. ~~The focus group~~
278 ~~discussions were audio-recorded and machine-transcribed using the transcribe function in~~

279 [Microsoft Teams classic \(June 2023\), with transcription errors corrected only when it was](#)
280 [judged to have changed the meaning of the concepts of interest to the item identification](#)
281 [process. Transcripts were anonymized and original recordings were deleted after 30 days.](#)
282 The focus group discussions were moderated by one investigator (PW) and assisted by
283 another investigator (GEV). The discussion was structured according to the [SEVCO-bias](#)
284 domains used to organise the items extracted from the literature. For each domain, the
285 moderator presented the name of the bias [domain](#), the number of items that had been
286 associated with the bias from the literature-based component of the item bank, and the
287 definition of the bias ~~as from SEVCO~~. Discussion was paced by the moderator to attempt to
288 work through all domains across the two sessions. The order in which domains were
289 presented ~~varied was different~~ for each group, with priority given to domains that had overall
290 received less discussion [in previous focus groups](#) (with the exception that when starting a
291 discussion with a new group, a more intuitive domain would be chosen to get conversation
292 going). Participants were led in discussion of how the domain might be relevant to the *in vitro*
293 research context, and asked for examples from their practical research experience of how
294 systematic error can be introduced into an *in vitro* study. A third investigator (HMA)
295 participated in all sessions, taking back-up notes in case of technical failure and to support
296 any necessary correction of the machine-generated transcripts. The information shown to
297 the participants of each focus group is in Supplemental Material 3:-

298 Participants were given the option to ~~email~~ [send by email](#) their thoughts and considerations
299 on the relevance of the discussed bias domains and items for *in vitro* studies to the project
300 group ~~by email~~ within a week after each discussion. One comment was received and added
301 to the analysis.

302 [2.2 Issue Analysis](#)

303 ~~An overview of the item analysis~~ [The analytical process by which the bias issues abstracted](#)
304 [from the literature sources and focus groups are interpreted into items is shown in Figure 1.](#)
305 [In the first stage of issue analysis, bias-related issues were abstracted from the included](#)
306 [literature sources and the focus group transcripts. For the literature sources, two](#)
307 [investigators \(PW and GEV\) independently abstracted bias-related criteria from each source,](#)
308 [focusing on any section of a source that seemed to be presenting a list or table of study](#)
309 [quality criteria. They discussed and reconciled inconsistencies in the results of their](#)
310 [abstraction process.](#)

311 [The transcripts were independently annotated in Microsoft Word by two investigators \(HMA](#)
312 [and GEV\) for instances of participants indicating specific ways in which bias can be](#)

313 introduced into an *in vitro* study (see Supplemental Material 4). After each transcript was
314 independently annotated, the two copies were combined into a single document. Two
315 investigators (HMA and GEV) went through the combined document to reach a consensus
316 on annotation. After consensus was reached, one investigator (HMA) transferred the data
317 (time stamp, data extract, annotated text) to an Excel file.

318

319 ~~in the analysis, the – Interpretation. The criteria were interpreted by the investigators into~~
320 ~~the core internal validity concepts that each study appraisal criterion appeared to be~~
321 ~~addressing was interpreted, and these were then.~~

322 ~~**Step 3 – Normalisation** The normalised core concepts were normalised for~~
323 ~~linguistically consistency (Section 2.2.1). The normalised core concepts are called~~
324 ~~“bias items”. The bias items are the study properties that may be relevant for~~
325 ~~introduction of bias in results and/or their interpretation due to limitations in conduct,~~
326 ~~design, or reporting of a study.~~

327 ~~**Step 4 – Mapping onto bias domains:** To provide an organisational structure for the~~
328 ~~item bank the bias items were organized thematically by mapping onto bias domains~~
329 ~~(Section 2.2.2).~~

332 **Figure 1. Flow chart of the process of [analysing bias issues discovered in appraisal tools and focus group discussion](#). [The flow chart](#)**
333 **[shows how issues and appraisal tool criteria are](#) normalised ~~using criteria~~ to create item bank items, with illustrative examples from three criteria**
334 **sources (two tools and the focus group discussions). The flow chart shows progression from raw criterion, through interpretation into core**
335 **concepts, normalisation for linguistic consistency, and [the](#) classification of ~~each~~ item under [the most](#) relevant bias domain.**

336

2.2.11.2 Interpretation and normalisation

Abstracted study assessment criteria were interpreted and normalised into items in a iterative process by two investigators (GEV and PW) (Figure 1). Criteria were interpreted into individual statements of core concepts relevant to the assessment of internal validity of a study by each investigator independently, based on their understanding and interpretation. The two investigators GEV and PW resolved differences in interpretation of the core concepts through discussion and reconciliation, subsequently simplifying the statements core concepts into the simplest achievable linguistic consistent expression of the bias issue each item addressed. This process is referred to as "normalisation". In the normalisation process, we aimed to eliminate trivial differences in wording but preserved conceptual differences, even small ones, as these might be significant to the development of INVITES-IN in a way it would not be appropriate to anticipate during the item identification process. It should be noted that we also aimed to avoid making unwarranted assumptions in the data set as to what concepts the tool creators intended to represent by the words they were using. Therefore, some of the bias items resulting from the normalisation process may be overlapping and some may not be intuitive to interpret.

Some of the abstracted criteria were complex, where a tool compounded more than one potential source of bias into a single point of evaluation. These complexound criteria were split into multiple individual criteria. Therefore, the final number of items in the item bank may be higher than the number of criteria presented in the original literature sources. This is illustrated in Figure 1 where one signaling question from the SciRAP tool was eventually interpreted as two items, and one signaling question from Cooper et al. (2016) was interpreted as three items.

The focus group discussions were audio-recorded and machine-transcribed using the transcribe function in Microsoft Teams classic (June 2023), with transcription errors corrected only when it was judged to have changed the meaning of the concepts of interest to the item identification process. Transcripts were anonymized and original recordings were deleted after 30 days.

The transcripts were independently annotated in Microsoft Word by two investigators (HMA and GEV) for instances of participants indicating specific ways in which bias can be introduced into an *in vitro* study (see Supplemental Material 4). After each transcript was independently annotated, the two copies were combined into a single document. Two investigators (HMA and GEV) went through the combined document to reach a consensus

370 ~~on annotation. After consensus was reached, one investigator (HMA) transferred the data~~
371 ~~(time stamp, data extract, annotated text) to an Excel file.~~

372 The nine hours of focus group discussions yielded a large number of potential issues for
373 normalisation (n=911). ~~Therefore, it was not feasible to complete the full normalisation~~
374 ~~process in a timely fashion.~~ To reduce the size of the task, two investigators (PW and GEV)
375 did a first pass check of pre-analysed the transcript annotations, independently answering for
376 each annotated issue “Are you sure this is about bias?” and “Are you sure this is a new
377 item?”. Issues for which both investigators answered yes to both questions were advanced
378 directly to issue normalisation analysis. When investigators disagreed on either question,
379 they discussed their responses to come to agreement consensus on whether an item ought
380 to be excluded from or advanced to normalisation issue analysis. ~~When the investigators~~
381 ~~agreed they were uncertain about whether an annotated issue was new or about bias, the~~
382 ~~item it was advanced to normalisation. Issues that advanced to normalisation were~~
383 ~~processed in the same way as the study assessment criteria abstracted from the literature.~~

384 The next stage of issue analysis was conducted as an iterative process whereby two
385 investigators (GEV and PW) independently proposed their interpretation of the core bias
386 issues represented by an abstracted criterion or discussion point. Sometimes this involved
387 splitting complex criteria or discussion points into multiple individual concepts. The
388 investigators then compared their interpretations and reconciled differences through
389 discussion. This process resulted in a list of draft items for the item bank.

390 The draft items often had redundant wording or otherwise lacked linguistic precision. These
391 items were therefore reformulated a final time to remove unnecessary phrasing and
392 eliminate as many trivial linguistic differences as was possible. The reformulations were
393 proposed by PW and commented on by GEV, with disagreements about appropriate
394 formulation discussed by the two investigators until consensus was reached. This process
395 resulted in the final "normalised" set of items that constitute the item bank.

396

397 2.2.12 Domain mapping

398 2.1.3 Mapping items onto bias domains

399 Each item was mapped onto single categorised according to the single, best-fitting
400 bias domains relating to the item. by Categorisation decisions were made by one investigator
401 (PW), with another (-GEV) checking for agreement. Potential disagreements were resolved

402 by discussion. The bias domains and definitions were taken from the Scientific Evidence
403 Code System (SEVCO) research methods ontology (Alper et al., 2021b; FEVIR Platform
404 Version 0.80.0, 06.12.2022).

405 The list of domains and their definitions and identifiers are shown in Table 2.

406 The SEVCO domains were We chose the SEVCO domains ~~chosen~~ because of the grounding
407 and consensus process used for developing their definitions (Alper et al., 2021a), making
408 them, in our opinion, the most comprehensive and robust available to us at the time of the
409 conduct of our work, with ~~Oh one SEVCO bias domain was~~ We modified modified one domain
410 (“Timing of Study Termination Bias” SEVCO:00370, originally “Early study termination bias”)
411 to reflect potential for bias from allowing an *in vitro* study to run on longer than originally
412 planned, as well as from being stopped earlier than planned, and We added two bias
413 domains added to support classification and analysis (“Metabias” and “Other”)- The domains
414 that were added are for organisational purposes, to capturing items that did not fit under the
415 other bias domains, and not intended to represent “true” biases (“metabias” was used for
416 items that appear to affect multiple bias domains; “other” was for items that did not appear to
417 relate to any bias domain). These domains are not intended to represent “true” biases. Four
418 SEVCO domains (Mixed Methods Research Bias; Predictive Model Research Bias;
419 Qualitative Research Bias; Synthesis Bias) ended up with no items and were therefore
420 unused in the item bank. The list of domains and their definitions is shown in Table 2.

421 ~~The SEVCO domains were chosen because of the grounding and consensus process used~~
422 ~~for developing their definitions (Alper et al., 2021a), making them in our opinion the most~~
423 ~~comprehensive and robust available to us at the time of the conduct of our work. Four~~
424 ~~SEVCO domains (Mixed Methods Research Bias; Predictive Model Research Bias;~~
425 ~~Qualitative Research Bias; Synthesis Bias) ended up with no items and were therefore~~
426 ~~unused in the item bank.~~

427 **Table 2. Bias domains used for classifying item bank items.**

Bias Domain	Definition	Source	Identifier
Analysis Bias	A bias related to the analytic process applied to the data.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00021
Attrition Bias	A bias due to absence of expected participation or data collection after selection for study inclusion.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00019

Bias Domain	Definition	Source	Identifier
Choice-of-Question Bias	A bias in research design in which the research question (that the study is designed to answer) is inappropriate for the context.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00018
Conflicted Interests Bias	A bias in which decision makers influencing research design, conduct, analysis or reporting have goals or motivations that conflict with scientific research objectives.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00027
Confounding Covariate Bias	A situation in which the effect or association between an exposure or outcome is distorted by another variable. For confounding covariate bias to occur the distorting variable must be (1) associated with the exposure and the outcome, (2) not in the causal pathway between exposure and outcome, and (3) unequally distributed between the groups being compared.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00016
Detection Bias	A bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00020
Timing of Study Termination Bias*	A bias due to the decision to end the study earlier or later than planned. <i>*Modified from the original SEVCO term, "early study termination bias", defined as "a bias due to the decision to end the study earlier than planned"</i>	SEVCO	SEVCO:00370*
Performance Bias	A bias resulting from differences between the received exposure and the intended exposure.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00017
Reporting Bias	A bias due to distortions in the selection of or representation of information in study results or research findings.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00023

Bias Domain	Definition	Source	Identifier
Selection Bias	A bias resulting from methods used to select subjects or data, factors that influence initial study participation, or differences between the study sample and the population of interest	SEVCO	SEVCO:00002
Metabias	A general distorting influence on investigator decision-making that may bias the results or findings of a study	Added by project team	INVITE:00003
Other	A distortion in results due to factors other than those described in the SEVCO terms	Added by project team	INVITE:00001

428

429 [2.34 Deviations from protocol](#)

430 We made the following changes to the methods [as planned/described](#) in the original protocol
431 (Svendson et al., 2023):

- 432 • We added the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Exposure (ROBINS-E) -tool
433 (Higgins et al., 2024) ~~(ROBINS-E Development Group)~~ to the set of literature sources, as
434 we judged it could be important in broadening the scope of the issues covered by the
435 item bank.
- 436 • We excluded the systematic review conducted by Tran et al. (2021) because it did not
437 present in its results or supplemental materials a list of issues or criteria applied by
438 ~~included the appraisal~~ tools.
- 439 • ~~The modification of “Early termination bias” and adding of two additional domains were~~
440 ~~not planned.~~
- 441 • ~~We modified the “Early termination bias” SEVCO domain to also cover potential for bias~~
442 ~~introduced by late study termination. We renamed the domain “Timing of study~~
443 ~~termination bias”. This was in response to identification of issues relating to the potential~~
444 ~~for bias from allowing an in vitro study to run on longer than originally planned, as well as~~
445 ~~from being stopped earlier than planned.~~
- 446 • ~~Two additional bias domains were included as a result of the collection of tomes~~
447 ~~metabias” (including bias items such as e.g. item 4048 “inappropriate deviation from~~

Commented [PW4]: Citation: Higgins JPT, Morgan RL, Rooney AA, Taylor KW, Thayer KA, Silva RA, Lemeris C, Akl EA, Bateson TF, Berkman ND, et al. 2024. A tool to assess risk of bias in non-randomized follow-up studies of exposure effects (ROBINS-E). Environ Int. 186(108602):108602. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2024.108602. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108602.

- 448 protocol" and item 107 "test system in general") and "other" (including e.g. the item 283
449 "other source of bias"). These were organisational domains to accommodate items that
450 did not seem to have a specific domain of application, either because they appeared to
451 have non-specific application or explicitly concerned biases that were not covered by
452 existing domains.
- 453 • We added the first-pass step to analysis of issues from the [FGD focus group discussions](#),
454 to make it feasible to analyse an unexpectedly large number of potential items.

455 3.3 Results

456 [405](#) [107](#) unique bias items of potential relevance for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro*
457 studies were assembled from the literature and the [FGD focus group discussions](#). After
458 removal of duplicates within and across all sources, [405 unique bias items were included in](#)
459 [the item bank](#). We abstracted from our included literature sources and focus group
460 discussions 414 appraisal criteria and discussion points of plausible relevance to the internal
461 validity of *in vitro* studies. After normalisation, this yielded 405 unique items in our item bank.
462 Because some items occur in more than one source, our eight sources contributed 497
463 items in total.

464 [The item bank is available in .xlsx format \(Microsoft Excel\) in Supplemental Materials 5. This](#)
465 [file consists of seven sheets, as follows:](#)

- 466 • [Sheet 0 "Information"](#). The information sheet that provides guidance on the
467 [contents of the item bank file](#).
- 468 • [Sheet 1 "Item Bank"](#). The item bank, consisting of the reference numbers, unique
469 [items \(n=405\), and the bias domains under which each item has been categorised](#).
470 [Each item has a unique reference number to facilitate identification and tracking](#)
471 [through the analysis process](#).
- 472 • [Sheet 2 "Items by Source"](#). The item bank, including the source and original
473 [criterion or discussion point from which each item was derived](#). Because some items
474 [appear in multiple sources, the total number of records in this sheet \(n=497\) is higher](#)
475 [than the total number of items \(n=405\)](#).
- 476 • [Sheet 3 "Abstracted Criteria"](#). The full list of criteria and discussion points
477 [abstracted from the literature sources and focus group discussions, that were](#)
478 [interpreted into the items](#).
- 479 • [Sheet 4 "Included Criteria"](#). The criteria and discussion points containing concepts
480 [that ended up being interpreted into items and included in the item bank. This sheet](#)

481 shows how the criteria and discussion points were interpreted into items by the
482 investigators.

- 483 • Sheet 5 "Excluded Criteria". The criteria and discussion points that were not
484 interpreted into items in the item bank.
- 485 • Sheet 6 "Lookups". The source for the drop-down lists of bias items, designed to
486 reduce data input errors when creating the item bank.

487 Sheets 1 and 2 have been set up with filters to assist with exploring the item bank, allowing
488 e.g. only items associated with analysis bias to be displayed (sheet 1), or only items
489 associated with a specific source (sheet 2). The sheets are locked but not password
490 protected to prevent accidental editing. To filter the data in the sheets, the user should right-
491 click the tab for the sheet they are interested in filtering and select "Pause Protection".

492 The relative contribution of items from different sources separated by bias domains is shown
493 in Figure 2.

494 Detection bias (n=104), performance bias (n=77), and selection bias (n=70) are the domains
495 with the most items. Two domains (choice-of-question bias and timing of study termination
496 bias) did not have any related items in the literature sources, with items coming exclusively
497 from focus group discussions (n=5 and n=3 respectively).

498 Items relating to confounding covariate bias (n=7) were contributed by tools designed for
499 assessing the internal validity of epidemiological studies. These were considered by the
500 focus groups as potentially important for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies that
501 use primary biological samples; however, as this type of study is outside the scope of
502 INVITES-IN at this time, this issue was not discussed in detail and the focus groups added
503 no further items for this domain.

504 Only three items relating to conflicted interest bias were derived from the literature sources.
505 The focus group discussions contributed six items, to give eight items in total under this
506 domain after removal of duplicates. Conflicted interest bias was considered important by the
507 focus groups, with several examples presented of where participants were concerned that
508 this had impacted studies; however, the groups found it challenging to identify specific
509 criteria for how conflict of interest could be assessed independently of the impact it has on
510 decisions about how to design, conduct, or report a study.

511 Metabias is a very heterogeneous domain. It includes issues such as “blinding of operator”
512 (item 299) that are both highly specific study design issues yet impact multiple bias domains.
513 Importantly, the metabias domain includes “inappropriate deviation from protocol” (item
514 4048). We believe is the only reference in the whole item bank to the potentially important
515 issue of inappropriate exploitation of researcher degrees of freedom (Wicherts et al., 2016)
516 when conducting and reporting research.

517 The two literature sources we included that were not originally designed for in vitro studies
518 (ROB2 for human randomised controlled trials and ROBINS-E for human observational
519 studies of environmental exposures) contributed 24% of the items in the item bank (118 of
520 497 items before deduplication). The focus group discussions contributed 28% of the items
521 in the item bank (139 of 497 items before deduplication).

522 An overview of the number of bias items identified from the different sources and the
523 organisation in bias domains is shown in Figure 2. An overview of each step in the process
524 of creating the item bank is shown in Supplemental Material 5. Supplemental material 5
525 This item bank is presented as a multi-sheet excel file in Supplemental Material 5 including
526 all abstracted study assessment criteria, the interpretations of the criteria into core internal
527 validity concepts addressed by each criterion, the bias items derived by normalisation of the
528 core concepts for linguistic consistency, the classification of bias items under relevant bias
529 domain, and the deduplication.

530 The R software was used to generate Figure 2, and the R Code for generating the Figure 2 is
531 available in Supplemental Material 6. Detection, performance, selection, and analysis bias
532 were the domains with the most items. Two domains (choice of question bias, timing of
533 study termination bias) were not covered in the literature at all, with items coming exclusively
534 from focus group discussions. Confounding covariates were issues in included tools, but for
535 *in vitro* contexts principally concern studies which use primary biological samples. Conflict of
536 interest bias was considered of importance by the focus groups, with several examples
537 presented of where participants were concerned that this had impacted studies; however,
538 the groups found it challenging to identify specific criteria for how conflict of interest could be
539 assessed independently of the impact it has on decisions about how to design, conduct, or
540 report a study. Metabias, combined with the small number of “other” biases, was a very
541 heterogeneous category. It included issues such as “blinding of operator” (item 299) that can
542 be both a highly specific feature of study design yet impact multiple bias domains.
543 Importantly, it also included “inappropriate deviation from protocol” (item 4048), which we

544 believe is the only reference to the potentially important issue of inappropriate exploitation of
 545 researcher degrees of freedom (Wicherts et al., 2016) in the whole item bank.

546
 547 **Figure 2. Unique bias items, disaggregated by source and in total from all sources.**

548 Note that the total count of ~~deduplicated~~ items ~~across from all~~ sources (column: ALL
 549 SOURCES) is lower than the sum of ~~deduplicated~~ items from individual sources (columns:
 550 Cooper, IRIS, etc.) because some items appear in more than one source and are
 551 deduplicated in the final count. We used the Obscure Reference Generator (Version 2.1;
 552 Esolang, 2014), to generate Figure 2, the code for generating the figure is available in
 553 Supplemental Material 6. (columns: Cooper, IRIS, ..., focus group discussion (FGD)), due to
 554 deduplication across the whole set yielding more duplicates than duplicate items within each
 555 subset by source.

4. Discussion

We have created a comprehensive item bank containing of 405 unique bias items that may be relevant of potential relevance for the assessment of the internal validity of *in vitro* toxicology studies. The discovery process included both literature and focus group discussions with *in vitro* research experts. We hope this provides a valuable dataset for informing the development of tools that include assessment of the internal validity of *in vitro* studies, and a methodology that is useful for appraisal tool development in general. Through our normalisation process we believe we advance on the methods recommended by Whiting et al. (2017) and used by Page et al. (2020), while by conducting focus group discussions we identified significantly more issues than we would have done through following an exclusively literature-based approach such as that of Whaley et al. (2024).

To support the interpretation and use of our item bank in tool development, and the reuse of our method, we discuss the following below:

- Our normalisation and exclusion decisions
- The importance of focus group discussions
- Some observations about the tools we included as literature sources
- Guidance on how to use the item bank

We believe that the combined use of a variety of published and widely used risk of bias tools covering potential sources of systematic biases that are currently considered relevant for human and animal studies in addition to *in vitro* studies and information collected from *in vitro* experts comprise a strength in the creation of the INVITES-IN item bank. We have created a comprehensive item bank containing 405 unique bias items that may be relevant for the assessment of the internal validity of *in vitro* toxicology studies. The discovery process included both literature and fgds with *in vitro* research experts. We believe that the combined use of literature including published and widely used risk of bias tools with information collected from *in vitro* experts comprise a strength in the creation of the INVITES-IN item bank. The FGDs were the single source that added the largest number of bias items, specifically linked to the *in vitro* area.

-

4.1 Uniqueness of the bias items Normalisation and exclusion decisions
Our process for analysing criteria from literature sources and discussion points from the focus group discussions into normalised items was naturally subjective and completed in finite time. We expect that additional rounds of analysis would have eliminated further trivial

590 [differences between items and reduced the number of items overall \(items 202 “exposure](#)
591 [misclassification” and 208 “misclassification of exposure” are a particularly obvious example](#)
592 [of where we missed conceptual duplicates\). Other researchers could reasonably argue that](#)
593 [differences between items such as 105 “storage of test compound” and 2097 “storage of test](#)
594 [materials” are functionally equivalent and that preserving the difference unhelpfully inflates](#)
595 [the number of items in the item bank.](#)

596 [Our counterargument to this point is we felt that preserving even small conceptual](#)
597 [differences might be significant to the development of an INVITES-IN appraisal tool in a way](#)
598 [we cannot anticipate during the item identification process. We felt that if we normalised](#)
599 [away subtle differences, we risked losing important nuance and context that we would not be](#)
600 [able to retrieve later. This could have a particular impact on the more detailed prompts,](#)
601 [elicitation questions, and guidance that will form part of the eventual INVITES-IN tool. We](#)
602 [therefore normalised items in such a way as to preserve detail, and it is in the post-Delphi](#)
603 [stage of INVITES-IN \(when we create the beta version of our tool\) that we will remove detail](#)
604 [in the items that is not helpful for our context.](#)

605 [Our exclusion decisions were similarly subjective. Other researchers may not agree with](#)
606 [them, and it is possible we excluded concepts that should have been part of our final item](#)
607 [bank. A limitation of our method is that we did not document all reasons for our exclusions](#)
608 [\(see Supplemental Materials 6, sheet 5\) as it was too time-intensive to give informative](#)
609 [reasons for hundreds of exclusion decisions based on sometimes lengthy discussion. In](#)
610 [general we would note that using a larger team of researchers to make exclusion and](#)
611 [normalisation decisions, and conducting more rounds of normalisation, would lead to](#)
612 [improved results. However, with hundreds of items and each round taking many person](#)
613 [hours \(we estimate two people need 20 hours of discussion for 400 items\), a decision must](#)
614 [be made as to the cost-benefit trade-off of running each round of analysis.](#)

615 [To compensate for limitations and potential differences of opinion around our approach and](#)
616 [resulting items, we have included in our item bank all the uninterpreted source criteria and](#)
617 [discussion points, to give other teams all the materials they need to reinterpret our data.](#)~~The~~
618 ~~conceptual differences between some of the 405 bias items are small and may also be~~
619 ~~overlapping. To preserve conceptual differences, even small ones, as these might be~~
620 ~~significant to the development of INVITES-IN in a way it would not be appropriate to~~
621 ~~anticipate during the item identification process. †These are still included in the item bank as~~
622 ~~separate unique items. This way we to avoid making unwarranted assumptions in the data~~
623 ~~set as to what concepts the tool creators intended to represent by the words they were~~

624 using. In the next phases of the creation of INVITES-IN, the item bank items will be analysed
625 to derive an overview of the items that are considered important for introduction of bias to in
626 vitro studies, and to identify thematic issues and specific prompts that are considered to be
627 important differences between the items. This will then be turned into a manageable number
628 of signaling questions in the tool and a guidance for the rating of the signaling questions.

629 It should also be noted that this study was a discovery exercise with the sole aim of
630 collecting items for the creation of our item bank. Any reinterpretation of original tools and
631 criteria for our specific purposes should not be interpreted as critique of those tools: it is a
632 linguistic process of simplification that removes detail and information about context, to make
633 it easier to identify and analyse as many as possible of the core internal validity concepts
634 being expressed by the tools in aggregate.

635 4.2 The importance of focus groups and including non *in vitro* tools
636 In our opinion, including expert opinion in the preparation of the item bank via focus group
637 discussions was very effective. The focus group discussions provided new insight into how
638 participants considered, contextualised, and defined the different aspects of bias,
639 significantly extending the range of issues that would have been covered had we focused
640 exclusively on the literature for our item discovery process. The focus group discussions
641 added a large number of items to analysis, detection, performance, and selection bias, with
642 the practical experience of the participants able to add many considerations to bias domains
643 of which the literature only had partial coverage. ~~Examples of where the focus group~~
644 ~~discussions contributed items to domains that would otherwise have been almost empty are~~
645 ~~conflicted interest and choice of question bias.~~

646 It is important to note that the first focus group contributed 74 new discussion items, the
647 second 30, and the third group 28. The fact that a large proportion of new items were still
648 being discovered in the third focus group discussion suggests that there are more items yet
649 to be discovered. Therefore, coverage of all critical aspects for the assessment of internal
650 validity in *in vitro* studies, even in our item bank, remains incomplete and additional focus
651 groups would still be of high value.

652 Our assumption that tools not designed for in vitro studies would be useful for in vitro
653 contexts was also validated by our results, with ROB2 and ROBINS-E contributing many
654 items that we otherwise would have missed had we excluded them.

655
656 [4.32 Characteristics](#) Observations about of validity assessment included tools
657 ~~When/While~~ interpreting assessment criteria into items ~~bank items highlights~~, we noted three
658 ~~characteristics/issues that of assessment tools that~~ may be informative for their future
659 development [of appraisal tools in general](#).

660 [4.3.1 Multiple issues covered by single criteria](#)

661 Firstly, there is a tendency for tools to collapse multiple points of evaluation into a single
662 criterion, [in a way that may be problematic](#). For example, the ~~raw criterion for~~
663 ~~item~~ [uninterpreted criterion number 126 \(see Supplemental Materials 5, sheet 2 – reference](#)
664 [numbers are in column B\) states: covers multiple aspects of exposure and use of positive](#)
665 [controls, stating_](#) “Was the exposure period, timing (i.e., cell passage number, insufficient
666 culture maturity for the adequate expression of mature cell markers; insufficient treatment or
667 measurement duration for the production of protein above the level of detection), frequency,
668 and duration of exposure sensitive for the assay/model system of interest, particularly in the
669 absence of a positive control?”. [This combines multiple aspects of exposure and use of](#)
670 [positive controls, into a single prompt](#). The ~~raw/uninterpreted~~ criterion ~~for item number~~ 130,
671 from the same tool, [states: “Are there concerns regarding the need for positive controls \(e.g.,](#)
672 [concerns that the effects of interest may be inhibited or otherwise poorly manifest in the test](#)
673 [system, for example due to differences from in vivo biology\)? If used, was the selected](#)
674 [positive test substance \(and dose\) reasonable and appropriate and was the intended](#)
675 [positive response induced?” This criterion](#) covers several additional aspects of [the use of](#)
676 [positive controls, use](#)-relating to the ability of a test system to manifest an outcome of
677 interest, ~~stating: “Are there concerns regarding the need for positive controls (e.g., concerns~~
678 ~~that the effects of interest may be inhibited or otherwise poorly manifest in the test system,~~
679 ~~for example due to differences from in vivo biology)? If used, was the selected positive test~~
680 ~~substance (and dose) reasonable and appropriate and was the intended positive response~~
681 ~~induced?”~~.

682 Combining multiple issues into a single evaluation criterion may not always ~~matter be~~
683 [problematic](#), for example when a criterion addresses two issues in a similar enough domain
684 that it may not make sense to divide them in a particular study assessment context ~~(e.g.~~
685 ~~SciRAP “The statistical methods and software used were described”, interpreted into the~~
686 ~~following two items 23 and 24: “Statistical methods used for analysing data”; “Software used~~
687 ~~for analysing data”).~~ However, on some occasions it may be important to separate these
688 issues, (a) if this could affect [the](#) transparency or repeatability of the appraisal process, (b) [it](#)
689 [could](#) affect reuse of data from the assessment when it is ambiguous what specific issue a

690 judgement relates to, or (c) if it leads to double-counting of issues when there is overlap of
691 common issues across two or more compound criteria.

692 4.3.2 "Study sensitivity" as an assessment domain

693 Secondly, some [study appraisal](#) tools are concerned with the "sensitivity" of study methods
694 (e.g. IRIS 2022, Cooper 2016). However, when mapping [items derived from sensitivity](#)
695 [concerns them](#) onto bias domains, many [of these sensitivity](#) items seemed to [be fit covered](#)
696 [be the detection bias definition and these were therefore mapped naturally onto](#) under the
697 domain of detection bias (e.g. [the items](#) "[Insufficient level of exposure](#)" (ref 53)53),
698 "[Insufficient duration of exposure](#)" (ref 54)54, "[Insufficient range of doses](#)" (ref 69)69,
699 "[Duration of exposure](#)" (ref 72)72). Others [seemed to be covered](#) fit under the [by the](#)
700 [mapped onto](#) performance bias [domain definition](#) (e.g. [the items](#) "[Method of administration](#)
701 [of exposure](#)" (ref 73)73, "[Route of administration of exposure](#)" (ref 74)74) [and then the](#)
702 reporting bias [domain definition](#) (e.g. [the items](#) "[Choice of analyses reported](#)" (ref 76)76,
703 "[Choice of reported analyses](#)"78) [and were mapped onto these domains](#), or [Some sensitivity](#)
704 [criteria](#) were excluded as relating to the precision [of a study](#) (e.g., [the uninterpreted criterion](#)
705 [the item](#) "[Are the numbers of exposed cases adequate to detect an effect in the exposed](#)
706 [population and/or subgroups of the exposed population?](#)" (ref 50)50) or [the external validity](#)
707 [of a study](#) (e.g. [the item criterion](#) "[Are the outcome ascertainment methods reliable and valid:](#)
708 [is the outcome under study a sensitive indicator of the health effect of interest?](#)" (ref 51)51)
709 [of a study](#).

710 While it is not necessarily important how issues relating to potential systematic error are
711 divided into assessment domains, having the same concept split across two or more
712 separate domains may add unnecessary complexity to an assessment process and
713 potentially increase the risk of double-counting appraisal factors. [For example, \(e.g., the](#)
714 [criteria items](#) "[Does the exposure assessment capture the relevant window of exposure?](#)" (ref
715 57)57 and "[Is the timing and duration of exposure relevant for the endpoints under study? If](#)
716 [the sensitive exposure window is unknown, is the exposure period wide enough to cover](#)
717 [likely possibilities?](#)" (ref 71)71) seem closely related but are different questions in the source
718 tool, [and so are](#) Similarly, [the criteria](#) "[Variable Control: Are all introduced variables with the](#)
719 [potential to affect the results of interest controlled for and consistent across experimental](#)
720 [groups?](#)" (ref 85) and [items 85 and](#) "[Are appropriate control groups for the study/assay type](#)
721 [included? Was there a need for the assay to include specific controls to reduce potential](#)
722 [sources of underlying bias?](#)" (ref 113) appear to be the covering aspects of the same issue
723 [twice in the same tool.](#)413).

724 -This observation should not be interpreted as a critique of the specific assessment tools, as
725 we are only making general observations across a dataset and not analysing specific tools in
726 detail. However, it may be worthwhile conducting a closer inspection and re-evaluation of the
727 principles and structure behind some study assessment processes, and its potential impact
728 on the validity of the results of the evaluation process using these tools.

729 [4.3.3 Existing tools lag expert knowledge](#)

730 Thirdly, ~~the domain~~ coverage of [all critical aspects for the assessment of](#) internal validity
731 ~~issues~~ by existing tools may not be optimal. The focus group discussions identified many
732 new issues and were the single-largest contributor of assessment items,
733 ~~contributing including~~ items to some domains that were completely unmentioned in the
734 existing tools that we sampled. [In vitro study methods are a fast-evolving field and any](#)
735 [appraisal tool for the domain will likely need regular updating to keep up with ongoing](#)
736 [developments.](#)

737 [4.4 Guidance on how to use the item bank](#)

738 [The item bank is a database of concepts and requires further analysis when creating an](#)
739 [appraisal tool – it is like an ingredient in a recipe which cannot be consumed directly off the](#)
740 [shelf. For the beta version of INVITES-IN we are using Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data](#)
741 [Analysis Software \(CAQDAS\) to identify clusters of related concepts under a range of](#)
742 [possible appraisal themes that we could potentially use for structuring our appraisal tool. We](#)
743 [expect the broad themes to provide structure in the form of domains or sections of the tool;](#)
744 [for similarities between clusters of related items to be interpretable into elicitation questions;](#)
745 [and for the more granular details of the items to inform specific prompts or detailed guidance](#)
746 [on how elicitation questions in the tool should be answered.](#)

747 [In this process, we are finding it helpful to preface an item with a phrase that prompts](#)
748 [reflection on how the concept being expressed could result in issues with the internal validity](#)
749 [of a study. For example, for the item “Conditions of maintenance of cell line” we might think](#)
750 [“Problems with conditions of maintenance of cell line that introduce bias” to keep us focused](#)
751 [on interpreting the item for our task. A different team using our item bank to create a](#)
752 [reporting checklist might prefer to interpret items for their context as follows: “Problems with](#)
753 [reporting the conditions of maintenance of the cell line that compromise the reproducibility of](#)
754 [the study”. Our item bank is intended as a general resource, which means the user must](#)
755 [interpret the items for their specific context.](#)

756 [The number of new items per ~~FGD~~ focus group discussion group decreased from 74 in the](#)
757 [first group, to 30 in the second, and 28 in the third. The fact that new items were still being](#)

758 ~~discovered in the third focus group discussion suggests that there are more items yet to be~~
759 ~~discovered and that the coverage of all critical aspects for the assessment of internal validity~~
760 ~~domain coverage for potential bias issues inaround *in vitro* studies remains incomplete.~~

761 It should be noted that this study was a discovery exercise with the
762 sole aim of collecting items for the creation of our item bank. The six
763 tools from which we abstracted items were tools for assessment of
764 human studies, animal experimental studies, and/or in vitro studies,
765 and these were chosen because we considered that a tool may
766 contain items potentially informative for in vitro studies although it was
767 not designed for such studies. Any reinterpretation of original tools
768 and criteria for this purpose should not be interpreted as critique: it is
769 a linguistic process of simplification that removes detail and
770 information about context, to make it easier to identify and analyse as
771 many as possible of the core internal validity concepts being
772 expressed by the criteria.

773 4.3 Limitations in the creation of the item bank

774 These bias items were collected from Aa selection of the available
775 validity assessment tools were used to identify bias items variety of
776 published sources capturing potential sources of systematic biases
777 that are currently considered relevant for human and animal studies
778 in addition to in vitro studies. Inclusion of additional tools as sources
779 may lead to identification of additional bias items. The extraction of
780 study assessment criteria from the literature were conducted by the
781 same two persons who also interpreted, normalised and mapped the
782 items onto the bias domains. A potential limitation of this type of
783 discovery work is that it involves a succession of subjective decisions
784 that may have resulted in different codes and items if it had been
785 conducted by other persons, potentially with better optimized final
786 normalisation of criteria that is more reflective of community
787 understanding of the issues. On the other hand, running such a
788 process with multiple participants would be much more time-
789 consuming, therefore we think that the use of the same two persons
790 for all these judgements results in a reasonable level of consistency
791 in judgement and timeliness of analysis, while our documentation
792 renders the process transparent and hopefully relatively
793 straightforward for other researchers to build on in future.

794 4.4 Importance of focus groups Strengths

795 ~~Add heading: Importance of focus groups [then rewrite around this —~~
796 ~~we have somehow underplayed this important point]. In our opinion,~~
797 ~~including experts in the preparation of the item bank is a strength in~~
798 ~~our methodology, and doing this through focus group discussions~~
799 ~~worked very well. The FGD~~~~focus group discussions~~ provided new
800 insight into how participants considered, contextualised, and defined
801 the different aspects of bias, significantly extending the range of
802 issues that would have been covered had we focused exclusively on
803 the literature for our item discovery process. The FGD~~focus group~~
804 ~~discussions~~ added a significant number of items to analysis,
805 detection, performance, and selection bias, with the practical
806 experience of the participants able to add many considerations to
807 bias domains of which the literature only had partial coverage.
808 ~~Examples of where the FGD~~~~focus group discussions~~ contributed
809 items to domains that would otherwise have been almost empty are
810 conflicts of interest and choice of question bias.

811 Overall, we believe the item bank fulfills its purpose and will be a
812 valuable dataset of potential bias concepts that can support the
813 development of tools for the assessment of *in vitro* studies in the field
814 of toxicology.

815 ~~Add: better method than individually reviewing study appraisal tools.~~

816 5. Conclusion

817 We have created a comprehensive item bank of 405 unique bias items that may be relevant
818 for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies. ~~These bias items were collected from a~~
819 ~~variety of published sources capturing potential sources of systematic biases that are~~
820 ~~currently considered relevant for human and animal studies in addition to *in vitro* studies.~~

821 The inclusion of ~~FGD~~~~focus group discussions~~ with *in vitro* experts was of significant value in
822 our method, adding more than a hundred additional bias items and enhancing our
823 understanding of the challenges associated with assessing *in vitro* studies. ~~We believe that~~
824 ~~both the our method used to create the comprehensive item bank, and the item bank itself,~~
825 ~~will be useful for other researchers creating validity assessment tools. The item bank will be~~
826 ~~used in the next Delphi study for the creation of the INVITES-IN tool for assessing internal~~
827 ~~validity of *in vitro* toxicology studies. Overall, we believe our~~the item bank ~~fulfills will beto be~~
828 ~~a valuable dataset of potential bias concepts that can support the development of tools for~~
829 ~~the assessment of *in vitro* studies in the field of toxicology.~~

830 [Project governance](#)
831 [This study is part of the project “Next Generation Risk Assessment in Practice” \(VKM, 2023\),](#)
832 [included in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals \(PARC\)](#)
833 [\(PARC, 2023\). A project group is responsible for the creation of INVITES-IN. A scientific](#)
834 [advisory group consisting of experts in methods for tool development, systematic review](#)
835 [methods, chemical risk assessment, toxicology, and/or *in vitro* models has been established](#)
836 [to provide the project group with strategic guidance and support during the process of](#)
837 [creating INVITES-IN \(VKM, 2023\).](#)

838 [Abbreviations](#)

839 FGD: focus group discussion

840

841 ~~PG: project group~~

842 ~~SAG: scientific advisory group~~

843 SEVCO: Scientific Evidence Code System

844

845 ~~SR: systematic review~~

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849 [Definitions / Glossary](#)

850 The definitions have been updated since publication of our study protocol (Svensen et al.,
851 2023).

852 **Bias** is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual
853 studies or across studies. Systematic error may be introduced through limitations in the
854 design, conduct, or reporting of a study.

855 **Bias domains** are a conceptual framework for organising the limitations in conduct, design,
856 or reporting of a study that have affected the internal validity of a study. Bias domains in the
857 present study include but are not limited to detection, performance, and selection bias.

858 **Criteria** are the issues that have to be fulfilled for bias to be avoided. In tools for evaluation
859 of risk of bias, the users of the tool will often answer signalling questions in order to
860 determine whether the criteria have been fulfilled.

861 **Internal validity** is the extent to which the design, conduct, and reporting of a study are
862 likely to have prevented bias.

863 **Items** are linguistically minimalist expressions of study assessment concepts. In the present
864 study, “items” are derived by a normalisation process from study assessment criteria
865 presented in study appraisal tools and described in focus group discussions, that potentially
866 relate to the internal validity of an *in vitro* study.

867 **Item bank** is a database of items.

868 **Normalisation** is the process of organizing data in a database. In the present example, this
869 involves identifying and consistently expressing the core bias concepts underlying the
870 assessment criteria applied by study appraisal tools.

871 **Risk of bias** is the potential for systematic error in the results or findings of a study or across
872 studies. Tools for assessing the internal validity of studies tend to focus on risk of bias, as
873 bias itself cannot usually be directly measured.

874 **Signalling questions** are the questions that the users of a validity assessment tool answer
875 in order to determine whether a given set of assessment criteria have been fulfilled.

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885 [Ethical considerations](#)

886 Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian
887 Institute of Public Health on February 7th, 2022, (Archive No 22/04212). Ethical approval is
888 not relevant since no biological materials or information on health will be collected.

889 [Declaration of interests](#)

890 The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship,
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892 [Authors contribution](#)

893 **Conceptualization:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, Gro H. Mathisen, Trine Husøy,
894 Camilla Svendsen, and Paul Whaley.

895 **Data curation:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, and Paul Whaley.

896 **Formal analysis:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, Gro H. Mathisen, Trine Husøy, and
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899 **Investigation:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, and Paul Whaley.

900 **Methodology:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, Gro H. Mathisen, Trine Husøy, Camilla
901 Svendsen, and Paul Whaley.

902 **Project administration:** Gro H. Mathisen.

903 **Software:** Trine Husøy.

904 **Visualization:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, Gro H. Mathisen, Trine Husøy, and Paul
905 Whaley.

906 **Writing - original draft:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, Gro H. Mathisen, and Paul
907 Whaley.

908 **Writing – review & editing:** Gunn E. Vist, Heather M.R. Ames, Gro H. Mathisen, Trine
909 Husøy, Camilla Svendsen, Anna Beronius, Emma Di Consiglio, Ingrid L. Druwe, Thomas
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